

The Astronomical Event Observatory Network on SOAR: Implementation and First Results

César Briceño on behalf of the AEON collaboration

Scientists: C. Briceño (SOAR/NSF's NOIRLab), B. Miller (Gemini/NSF's NOIRLab), S. Ridgway (CSDC/NSF's NOIRLab), R. Street (Las Cumbres)

Developers: D. Gomez, O. Estay, R. Cantarruti (CTIO/NSF's NOIRLab); S. Torres (SOAR/NSF's NOIRLab); J. Nation, E. Heinrich, M. Bowman, N. Volgenau (Las Cumbres); S. Fanale (formerly at University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)

Observatory Representatives: L. Storrie-Lombardi (Las Cumbres), J. Elias (SOAR/NSF's NOIRLab), A. Adamson (Gemini/NSF's NOIRLab), S. Heathcote (CTIO/NSF's NOIRLab), A. Bolton (CSDC/NSF's NOIRLab)

Figure 1: Nightscape of the SOAR and Gemini South telescopes on Cerro Pachón. These are the first 4–8m-class facilities that will be integrated into the AEON system. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/B. Quint)

Introduction

The Astronomical Event Observatory Network (AEON) is a collaboration among NSF’s NOIRLab, Las Cumbres Observatory, the Southern Astrophysical Research (SOAR) 4.1m Telescope, and the international Gemini Observatory 8.4m telescopes. The goal is to develop an ecosystem of facilities to provide rapid and efficient follow-up observations of alerts created from modern astronomical surveys, with particular emphasis on the new windows into time-domain and multi-messenger astronomy brought about by the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) on the Vera C. Rubin Observatory 8.4m Simonyi Survey Telescope on Cerro Pachón, Chile.

AEON is envisioned as a collection of world-class telescopes (Figure 1) that can be accessed on demand through highly automated tools, operating in the wider context of astronomical surveys, alert brokers such as ANTARES (Saha et al. 2016, SPIE, 9910, 99100F), Target and Observation Manager systems (TOMs; Street et al. 2018, SPIE, 10707, 1070711), observing facilities, and data archives. To deliver on the goal of responding within minutes to hour timescales to survey alerts with appropriate follow-up observations, all of these elements need to interact programmatically with each other in a sequence of steps following a survey discovery.

AEON builds on the extensive experience of Las Cumbres Observatory in running a worldwide network of 1m and smaller telescopes. Early on it was decided that the SOAR 4.1m Telescope on Cerro Pachón would be an ideal pathfinder facility to develop the required software tools,

capabilities, and operational experience for bringing 4m-class and larger telescopes into the Las Cumbres system. SOAR and Gemini South, with their flexible instrument suites, and the Victor M. Blanco 4m Telescope, with its DECam wide-field imager, are the natural “first-line responders” for alerts from the LSST.

Here we describe the implementation of AEON-mode observing at the SOAR telescope and the results after 2019B, our first semester of operations in shared-risk mode.

Implementing AEON at SOAR

The Goodman spectrograph, the facility workhorse, was the first instrument to be offered (<http://www.ctio.noao.edu/soar/content/goodman-high-throughput-spectrograph>). SOAR would be operated in “AEON mode” on selected nights during a given semester, the actual number dictated by the total time approved for all programs requesting this new mode by the NOIRLab Time Allocation Committee and other SOAR partners.

A base requirement was that the AEON queue be highly automated, with no intervention or target decision-making required from the Telescope Operators (TOs) who would be carrying out the observations, supervised by existing support scientists. The SOAR AEON queue would be externally generated, in an automated and unsupervised way, by the Las Cumbres scheduling software. Because the Goodman instrument control software was not designed to be run programmatically, remote operation capability had to be added.

Figure 2: Architecture of the SOAR Queue Manager (SQM) software. The SQM handles communications with the Las Cumbres scheduler via a common API. Communication with the instrument and telescope is handled via sockets through a TCP/IP protocol.

The required software development was carried out by staff at Las Cumbres, the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) Information Technology group, SOAR, and the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC–Chapel Hill), with the following charges:

- Define a common Application Programming Interface (API) to allow an observation request from the scheduler to be received, interpreted, and parsed as commands to the telescope and instrument at SOAR and for the resulting data files to be transmitted to both the Las Cumbres archive and the Astro Data Archive at NSF’s NOIRLab.
- Modify the Las Cumbres automated scheduler software to handle SOAR/Goodman.
- Develop scripting capabilities for the Goodman spectrograph.
- Develop the SOAR Queue Manager (SQM) software (Figure 2), with a web-based interface for the SOAR TOs, to handle all communications with Las Cumbres and with the SOAR telescope and the Goodman instrument.

This effort spanned three major phases, starting in late 2017 with the first visit of Las Cumbres staff to La Serena and culminating with the demonstration of AEON on SOAR in semester 2019B.

The work was carried out on schedule, and we had our first on-sky nights of testing AEON on 20 March and 15 April 2019. Classifications for several SN were published (Cartier et al. 2019, ATel, 12671, 1).

2019B Semester: Testing AEON on SOAR

We enrolled as beta testers eight approved science programs for 2019B that were a good match to AEON, totaling a maximum of 200 hours distributed over 20 nights. The science spanned a wide range of use cases, ranging from imaging of Near-Earth Objects (NEOs; Principal Investigator [PI]: N. Moskovitz, Lowell Observatory) and a study of asteroids with small perihelion distances (PI: M. Knight, University of Maryland) to time-domain spectroscopy of solar-like pre-main sequence stars in Orion (PI: T. Thanathibodee, University of Michigan), spectroscopic characterization of microlensing sources (PI: R. Street, Las Cumbres Observatory), spectroscopic classification of Young Supernovae (PI: R. Foley, University of California,

Figure 3: AEON workflow on SOAR. The user submits targets via the web-based Las Cumbres Observatory Observations Portal or via a TOM or custom Python script with the appropriate API. Observation requests are received at SOAR by the SQM and parsed as commands to the Goodman instrument and the Telescope Control System (TCS). The TCS in turn controls systems inside the optical Instrument Support Box (ISB), which carries auxiliary systems including the comparison lamps and mirrors. Data are sent to both the Las Cumbres and the NSF's NOIRLab Astro Data Archive as soon as the files are written on disk. At present, the users mostly retrieve their data through the Las Cumbres portal. SOAR TOs run the SQM software. Currently, the only interactive parts are acquiring the guide star and putting the science target on-slit. These two steps are done by the TO.

Santa Cruz), a multi-band, variability imaging search for RR Lyrae stars in ultra-faint dwarf galaxies (PI: C. Martínez, Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory), spectroscopy of gamma-ray blazar candidates (PI: F. Massaro, Observatorio Astrofisico di Torino), and determination of spectroscopic galaxy redshifts at low galactic latitudes (PI: L. Macri, Texas A&M).

These programs used the Goodman spectrograph in one or more of the following configurations: a low-resolution spectroscopic mode, using the 400 l/mm grating in M1 (300–700nm) and M2 (500–900nm) setups, with the 1 arcsec wide long slit, and 2x2 binning, at a resolution $R \sim 900$. A high-resolution mode used the 2100 l/mm grating centered at 650nm and the 0.45 arcsec wide long slit, providing a resolution $R \sim 12000$ and 63nm coverage. Imaging was done in 2x2 binning (plate scale = 0.3 arcsec/pixel) with the Sloan set of g, r, and i filters, and a wide VR filter.

Users were able to submit targets at any time for any of the scheduled nights and could do so either manually using the Las Cumbres Observation Portal or programmatically via a TOM or custom Python scripts using APIs. Most users accessed their data through the Las Cumbres portal. In

Figure 3, we show the schematic workflow of AEON on SOAR.

During semester 2019B, we had a total of 185 hours available for scheduling. We lost 53.2 hours to weather (28.7%) and 10.3 hours to technical problems (5.6%; including the loss of internet connectivity, issues with the scheduler software, and problems with the telescope or instrument). We therefore had 121.7 effective hours to observe. We were on-sky 113.7 hours (~93%) and observed on average 8 targets/night, or ~1h/target. This includes overheads to slew the telescope, on-slit target acquisition (for spectra), changes in configuration (many targets were observed in both 400 l/mm grating configurations), and readout time.

Some imaging programs, such as the ones studying moving Solar System objects, obtained hour-long sequences of short exposures on a given object. The setup of the required non-sidereal rates was automated specifically for AEON operations and is handled by the SQM software, which connects with the JPL HORIZONS database and downloads the ephemeris for the start of the observation. No intervention from the TO is required.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the web-based interface to the Python live Goodman spectroscopic pipeline, showing a fully reduced spectrum of a standard star. It features basic interactive visualization tools that allow zooming into particular regions, coordinates of the mouse position, and saving a view to a png file. Analysis capabilities such as equivalent width and signal-to-noise measurements will be added in future versions.

The raw data files were transferred in real time to both Las Cumbres and the NSF’s Astro Data Archive. Users could access their data a few minutes after the observations had been made.

The Future: 2020A and Beyond

For the start of semester 2020A, we implemented the observation of a spectrophotometric standard star every AEON night. This is configured in the SQM by the TO and is executed in an automatic way, the software selecting the star closest to the current position of the telescope, setting up the spectrograph, and selecting the appropriate exposure time. These observations are done ideally in twilight, before the start of the science queue, and they are publicly available to all users.

During semester 2019B, we only provided raw data files. For semester 2020A, we are offering, in beta-testing mode, the web-based live data pipeline for Goodman (Torres-Robledo and Briceño 2019, ASPC, 523, 203), which allows SOAR-AEON users to obtain extracted, wavelength-calibrated one-dimensional spectra seconds after the data have been written to disk and visualize them in their browser without the need to download any software (Figure 4). This product was not originally within the scope of the

AEON-SOAR implementation plan, but because we made significant advances, we decided to offer it for testing by our semester 2020A users. The live version is based on our Goodman offline pipeline available at GitHub (https://github.com/soar-telescope/goodman_pipeline) and fully documented (<https://goodman.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>).

In the future, we expect requests for the Goodman Blue camera and some additional configurations and the addition of other instruments such as the TSpec near-IR spectrograph (<http://www.ctio.noao.edu/soar/content/triplespec41>). Further engaging users from the SOAR partners—Brazil, Chile, Michigan State, and the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill—would add more AEON time, offering better cadence for time-domain programs and better chances of observing transients. For semester 2020A, we are already supporting one Chilean program. We are also working to automate the guide star and target slit acquisition.

AEON on SOAR brings a new window of opportunity not only for time domain and multi-messenger astronomy but also for programs with large numbers of targets over the sky and standard setups that would be able to observe during many nights through a semester.